

LINGUISTIC UNITS REPRESENTING THE CATEGORY OF STATE IN ENGLISH
LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes units representing the category of state in English and their expression in sentence structure. Also at the syntactic level, using comparatively typologically precise linguistic methods, the category of stativeness and devices with stative units were studied.

Key words: stative units, stative category, linguistic method, syntactic analysis.

Introduction

The category of stativeness, which is considered one of the important problems in contemporary linguistics, especially in the unrelated English and Uzbek languages, is used in the grammar of both languages. In English grammar, the state category is a category that indicates the state of the person or object at a certain time, mental or physical mood, standing in a certain place or directed to a certain goal. In English, the status category reflects the state of the subject and object that it expresses, with a broad meaning. The English linguist B.I. Ilish gave the following description of the categories that can be used instead of the words representing the status category in English: "Words expressing the status category, when they enter the adverbial category, do not only express their meaning, but become the complement of the sentence and expand its meaning" [3,31].

Literature analysis

In world linguistics, the status category is a constant focus of attention of scientists. Linguists who do studies to learn this category by the help of the materials in English, Uzbek and Russian, such as L.V. Shcherba, V.V. Vinogradov, B.I. Ilish, B.S. Haimovich, B.I. Rogovskaya, O.E. Filimonova, Andrew Koontz, N. Sweet, A.A. Abduazizov, U.U. studies are noteworthy.

We can observe that there are different approaches to the study of the stative category. In particular, the fact that it is related to an independent word group among some linguists has caused various discussions. The English linguist B.I. Ilish says that in most cases the words denoting stativeness depend on the verb [5;31], while B.S. Haimovich and B.I. Rogovskaya have mentioned that they complement "adlinks"- adverbs [4 ; 200]. V.V. Vinogradov stated that he believes that the category of stativeness complements the quality and can be used in its place.

Research methodology

In English, the words representing the status category can be used independently in a sentence according to the meaning and content structure, but are not considered an independent word group. When expressing the internal structure of the sentence or when analyzing the sentence paradigmatically or syntagmatically, it mainly expresses the subject or the object state. In the sentence, the state can represent the mental state of the person (ashamed, aware); physical condition of the person (astir, afoot); mental state of the object (afire, ablaze, aglow); can represent the object's spatial position (askew, awry, aslant).

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-4, ISSUE-3

For example: ... *Aliberty, feeling responsible for the cook's departure, and being afraid he would be punished.*

Or we can see that it can be replaced by another word group by using case words without the a-prefix, but even then it is not an independent word group.

For example: *I was laid low by flu, just before my exams. (in a poor or depressed state).*

His face wore a threatening though somewhat satisfied expression, while he pointed his long finger at the girl.

At the same time, we can find that the status category is similar in meaning to the adjective or in some situations it can be a substitute for the adjective. Here, as Professor O'.U.Usmanov pointed out, adjectives express a characteristic, words denoting the status category denote a state, secondly, adjectives have degree categories, but words denoting a state do not have such a category, and thirdly, this word We should not forget the words that emphasize that the functions of z groups in the sentence are not the same.

For example: *eager curiosity-curiosity agog- I was very unpopular because of my curiosity about other people's affairs.*

There is a feature of adjectives that adjectives and adjectives can independently express the thought that they want to express, without paying attention to the analogy of the case category:

- **mental state - happy, joyful;**
- **physical condition of a person -refreshed, healthy;**
- **expresses the state of action of the object or subject, i.e. - busy, functioning, active, employed**

Another aspect of the status category that is different from the adjective and not an independent word group is that we can prove it by contrasting the natural manifestations of similar adjectives with their substitutes. We know that "statives" cannot be used instead of adjectives. Because there are no degree categories in it. The problem of the status category is that the words representing it have the characteristics of being expressed in different categories. They can appear as a predicate expressing a verb in a sentence, but cannot be a full adjective. In particular, when complete adjectives indicate a state by approaching the possessor, the degree is evaluated based on the basis. Words that evaluate the level cannot be used in the function of syntax indicating the status. It can be seen that the words denoting the status category according to their syntactic structure do not express the degree of quantity, but they are capable of expressing general qualities when compared analytically.

For example: *Of us all, Jack was the one most aware of the delicate situation in which we found ourselves.*

I saw that the adjusting lever stood far more askew than was allowed by the directions.

If we study the case from the semantic and structural point of view, it was seen that it can take the place of a noun, verb, adjective, and adverb as a substitute for a word in terms of formation. In English, depending on the usage of the case category, it can come together with other word groups in the sentence or come in their place in a free state and give the meaning of the state. In

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-4, ISSUE-3

main sense, the situation itself enters the category of adverb and expresses the situation more in itself, while other categories can freely express it according to the action and request. In English, the category of state is formed by adding a verb, a noun, a pronoun, and an adjective. In the theoretical and practical grammar of the English language, there are views that The category of state (The statives) is divided into a separate group of words. But it was mentioned above that accepting it as a separate set of words is one of the issues that requires debate among linguists. The changes of state in English are expressed in Uzbek in the same way. We cannot define the category of stativeness as an independent or separate word group within both languages. At the morphological level of both languages, when the case category is given as a participle in the sentence structure of the lexical units, in English it is understood through the personal form of the linking verb to be and the verbs denoting the case.

For example: *It was the crying from down below that woke me up that hot night(P.B).*

It was the crying... --- It felt cryness --- It is in the state of cry

In English, case is expressed not only in its singular form, but some linguists L.V. Shcherba and V.V. Vinogradov regard it as an independent set of words, in which they can acquire a special meaning by expressing a substantial predicative adjective. . The fact that it comes in the form of a predicative, that is, a participle (verb) is the reason why it is included in the verb group and cannot be a separate group in many cases. In English, the situation is formed only based on experiences and physical and mental conditions of a person. When analyzing the sentences with syntactic units representing the situation into components and syntaxes, they can act as nuclear or secondary clauses in the sentence structure.

For example: *He is trouble.*

I want you to be trouble.

We cannot create a situation without linking these sentences to a verb or an adjective. The verb interprets the actions of a person not only through his inner world. There are verbs that come without the prefix a-, and they also express stativeness in the sentence in the case of relative movement of the action in one rhythm. Among these sentences, we can consider stative verbs, which are one of the main objects of the science of aspectology, as units representing stative syntax in grammar. Although units such as "love", "hate", "agree", "hear", "satisfy", "recognise", "understand" are not called stative words, they are understood as a group of verbs and are used in a sentence as verbs.

For example: *It was the crying from down below that woke me up that hot night.*

We interpret the expression of the case category by the elements of the verb group according to the tense aspect in the case where the verbs are used alone. Verbs have different tenses, so if a verb is used in the simple tense, it may not indicate the exact situation.

For example: *to sleep*
to cry

These verbs may not indicate a state without the suffix +ing, which is the present continuous verb suffix. Because it only expresses an action and does not express a state. We use the continuous form of the verb to express the situation.

For example: *No, not talking-quarreling.*

It was crying.....

This idea is expressed in O.E. We can see that Filimonova emphasized it in her auto-abstract entitled "Stative Syntax in the Structure of English Sentences". After all, we can find the state only in the continuous form of the verb.

For example: *He was adrift on the shoreless tides of delirium, speaking very quickly.*

He was mad going up every Sunday.

Cordelia was perfectly at ease, rejoicing in the food.

She was still sleeping. – She was still in a state of sleeping.

I was adrift in a strange sea. – I was drifting in a strange sea.

We use a number of linguistic methods in order to reveal the aspects of the stative category that are abstract to us. The great linguist Ferdinand de Saussure divides the language system into expressive and being expressed, and Wilhelm von Humboldt calls it “nomema” and “semema”. Through them, the function and place of stative units in the sentence is determined based on the component analysis of the sentences.

Analysis by components (AC) means the analysis of the mutual syntactic relations of the syntactic units involved in the sentence device using junctional models and their differential - syntactic links on the basis of component models. Each stative unit covers the "scope of meaning" of a group of units expressing stativeness. The meaning of each word in this series corresponds to the meaning of the other verb. They have a semantic commonality, but at the same time they differ from each other. On this basis, the meaning of each word can be divided into components (pieces) by contrasting and comparing them. Determining these differential meaning features is the main goal of component analysis.

The reason for analyzing the elements representing stativeness based on the methods of component analysis is to reveal the function and place of the words in the sentence, for what purpose they are being used at the moment. Words are interpreted in a sentence based on their semantic relations with other words. In the book "Language Construction: Analysis Methods and Methodology" by Professor T.A. Bushuy and Sh.S. Safarov, "The interpretation of meanings in this way makes it possible to divide different words into certain lexical-semantic groups based on the commonality of their semantic signs." Another important aspect of the analysis of the words denoting the situation based on the component method is to determine that the elements that make up it do not belong to only one group. The problem of an independent word group in it, as well as words denoting status, is that they belong to two groups at the same time. On the basis of component analysis, we can clarify the discussions of scientists on this issue and many unsolved issues.

Conclusion

There are morphological, syntactic, lexical and phonological approaches to the study of stative category in world linguistics. In our article, devices with stative units of the stative category were studied at the syntactic level using comparative-typologically accurate linguistic methods (transformational and syntax analysis, distributive analysis method). This linguistic method is a new approach to the analysis of stative units in both languages. In particular, determining the external and internal devices of stative unit sentences, that is, the syntactic connections of the syntactic units in the sentence, determining their differential - syntactic signs and semantic field, and their comparative analysis is one of the unique new approaches of modern syntactic typology.

The stative category has been recognized as a category in English and Uzbek languages, and having studied its aspects applied by foreign and Uzbek linguists, we have witnessed the achievement of several innovations in the analysis of stative syntactic units based on the comparative-typological linguistic methods that we approach. We have analyzed the fact that the category of stative in English is not considered a separate set of words in both languages, putting stative units into transformations, dividing them into statistical distributions and syntaxes. Through this, a number of questions that arose in both languages were answered. If we study the state from the point of view of semantics and structure, it was seen that it can take the place of a noun, verb, adjective, and adverb as a substitute for a word in terms of formation. In particular, the category of state is not used as an independent separate category in Uzbek grammar. When analyzing stative unitary sentences into components, it is desirable to determine the syntactic place of stative elements in the sentence, to determine the syntactic relations that connect them with other components, and to justify their differential syntactic features and their morphological features using the transformation method.

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